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MATHEMATICAL PHOBIA OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO CERTAIN DEMOGRAPHICAL VARIABLES

Sanjeev Kumar Jha, D.P. Tomar

Abstract

This research was an attempt to study Mathematical Phobia. The sample comprised of 192 students (96 girls and 96 boys) from secondary schools of Delhi. The sample was administered by a self-prepared questionnaire of Mathematical Phobia. The collected data was statistically analysed; for this purpose 't' and 'F' tests were calculated. Results of the research revealed that i) students from government schools have higher Mathematical Phobia, ii) students of age 14 year and more have higher Mathematical Phobia iii) boys have higher Mathematical Phobia iv) lower economic status students have higher Mathematical Phobia.

Mathematics should be visualized as the vehicle to train a child to think, reason, analyze, and particulate logically. Apart from being a specific subject it should be treated as a concomitant to any subject involving analysis and meaning (NPE, 1986).

Introduction

There is hardly anyone who doesn't experience some amount of fear and phobia, be it young or

old, rich or poor, learnt or ignorant, etc. It may be fear of failure, performance in public, fear of criticism, fear of looking small in the eyes of the others. Mathematical Phobia is an extremely irrational fear of Mathematics. It is the consequence of a continuous failure in either understanding or scoring good marks in Mathematics. It is an intense fear of failure in every branch of Mathematics.

- Sanjeev Kumar Jha** is a Research Scholar, B.M. College of Education, Jagdishpur, Sonapat, Haryana.
- Dr. D.P. Tomar** is a Principal with the same institution.

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The word 'phobia' is Greek; therefore any word that is connected to it should be Greek. To coin a new phobia name, it is proper to follow this rule. The word Mathematics is derived from the Greek word 'Mathematike'. So, Mathematical Phobia may be termed as "Mathematikephobia".

Mathematical Phobia may be caused because of the following reasons: i) Lack of ability to understand problem, ii) Lack of knowledge of basic concepts of Mathematics, iii) Lack of availability of good teachers of Mathematics, iv) Lack of practices of basic concepts of Mathematics, v) Continuous failure in solving a routine problem, vi) Lack of interest of students in Mathematics, vii) An extremely vast and complex curriculum, viii) Peers and teachers being critical of answer given by the student, ix) A lack of acceptance by other pupils as well as the teacher.

Preis et. al. (2001) studied how instructors help to overcome anxiety. They found that women, in particular older women, often experienced more mathematical anxiety as compared to their male counterparts. **Norman (2005)** focused his study on the attitude towards science and mathematics in relation to the sex of the secondary students. He found that

boys held a more positive attitude towards science and mathematics subjects as compared to that of girls. **M.T.V. Nagaraju (2006)** focused his research on the problems of the class 10th residential and non-residential school students in relation to certain demographical variables. He found 1) residential girl students have the high Mean score on mathematical problems. 2) residential school students whose monthly family income is up to Rs. 2000 have the high Mean score on the problem of mathematics. 3) distribution of mathematics achievement score of residential and non-residential school students is very near to normal distribution.

Justification of the Study

"5 lacks students failed out of 15 lakh students, who appeared for secondary examination in Mathematics in the board in the year 2004-05" cities.expressindia.com. It means 33.33% of students failed. Apart from this mass failure there are number of suicidal cases after the declaration of the board results. It shows that there is definitely something wrong at the bottom that is responsible for such mass failure. Most of the students have some kind of the problem with mathematics. It prompted the researcher to study the problem.

Objectives

Following objectives were stated –

- To study the difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at secondary level in relation to the Management of the school.
 - To study the difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at secondary level in relation to their Age.
 - To study the difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at secondary level in relation to their Sex.
 - To study the difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at secondary level in relation to their Economic Status.
- There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at the secondary level in relation to their Age.
 - There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at the secondary level in relation to their Sex.
 - There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at the secondary level in relation to their Economic Status.

Hypotheses

Below-cited hypotheses were formulated:

- There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and

Private school students at the secondary level in relation to the Management of the school.

- There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at the secondary level in relation to their Age.
- There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at the secondary level in relation to their Sex.
- There is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at the secondary level in relation to their Economic Status.

Methodology

In order to collect data properly the present investigation employed the “Survey Method” to study Mathematical Phobia of students at secondary level.

The Sample

Stratified random sampling technique was employed for the sampling.

The sample of the present study had comprised of 192 students studying in the government and private schools of Delhi at secondary level – 96 boys and 96 girls.

The sample from government schools: from 8th class 16 boys and 16 girls, from 9th class 16 boys and 16 girls, from 10th class 16 boys and 16 girls.

The sample from private schools: from 8th class 16 boys and 16 girls, from 9th class 16 boys and 16 girls, from 10th class 16 boys and 16 girls.

Tool Used

For the collection of the data the researcher used a self-prepared questionnaire.

The questionnaire was divided into three parts A and B.

Part A: Includes 20 questions to check the general attitude of the students towards Mathematics. Students are to put a tick (✓) mark on yes or no according to their choice.

Part B: Includes 10 statements, students are to rate themselves on the five-point scale.

Statistical Techniques Used

Statistical techniques like Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test and F-test were employed.

Table-1: Mean Difference in Mathematical Phobia in Relation to Management of the School at Secondary Level

Management of the School	N	Mean	SD	S.E _a	t-ratio
Government	96	14.04	2.93	0.59	6.50 (s)*
Private	96	10.20	5.05		

* at .05 level= 1.97

Analysis and Interpretation

As seen from Table 1 the test is significant at both the levels; hence the null hypothesis (H_0) i.e. there is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in relation to the Management of the school at secondary level is rejected. It means that there is a significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students at secondary level.

Figure-1

The Mean score of government school students (14.04) is greater than the private school students

Table-2: Summary of Analysis of Variance on Mathematical Phobia Score in relation to Age of the Student

Sources of Variance	Df	Sum of Square (SS)	Mean Square (MS)	F-ratio
SSB	$K-1=3-1=2$	84.46	42.23	3.12(S)*
SSW	$N-K=192-3=189$	2540.84	13.5	
Total	$N-1=192-1=191$	2652.30		

* at .05 level=3.04

(10.2). It means the government school students have higher Mathematical Phobia as compared to their private counterparts at secondary level.

As seen from Table 2, F-test is not significant at the .01 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted.

As seen from Table 3 F-test is significant at 0.05 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis (H_0) i.e. there is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in relation to their Age at secondary level is rejected. It means that there is a significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in relation to Age at secondary level.

Figure 2 show that the students of age more than 14 have highest Mathematical Phobia

Table-3: Mean Scores of Mathematical Phobia Test in Relation to Age Group

Age group	Number of the students	Mean
Up to 13 years	48	11.94
14 years	68	11.33
More than 14 years	76	12.80

(12.0) as compared to students of age group 14 and below 14 years at secondary level.

Figure-2

Also it can not be said that the Mathematical Phobia increased with the age, since the students of

age group up to 13 years have high Mean score (11.94) than the students of age group of 14 years. It may be because at the age of 14 years maturity level of the students is enough to understand the fundamentals of the Mathematics; also there is no stress of board exam (probably students are in 9th class). As they enter class 10th – age group more than 14 year – there is huge stress of board exam which does not allow students to learn freely.

As seen from Table 4 't'- test is not significant at the .01 level of significance; hence the null hypothesis (H_0) i.e. there is no significant difference between the Mean

scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in Relation to their Sex at secondary level is accepted.

The Mean score of Mathematical Phobia test of the boys (12.58) is greater than girls (11.66) (Figure 3). So the boys have more Mathematical Phobia than girls. It may be because the girls are harder working than the boys.

Figure-3

F-test is significant at both levels of significance, hence the null hypothesis (H_0) i.e. there is no significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government

Table-4: Mean Difference in Mathematical Phobia in Relation of Sex of the Students at Secondary Level

Sex	N	Mean	SD	S.E _d	t-ratio
Boys	96	12.58	4.007	0.54	2.25 (s)*
Girls	96	11.66	3.6		

* at .05 level=1.97

Table-5: Summary of Analysis of Variance on Mathematical Phobia Score in Relation to Economic Status of the Student

Sources of Variance	Df	Sum of Square (SS)	Mean Square (MS)	F-ratio
SSB	K-1=3-1=2	489.16	244.58	19.88(S)*
SSW	N-K=192-3=189	2325.614	12.30	
Total	N-1=192-1=191	2814.8		

* at .05 level=3.04

Table-6: Mean Scores of Mathematical Phobia Test

Economic status	Number of the students	Mean
Up to Rs 50000	76	13.66
Rs 50001-150000	88	11.76
More than Rs 150001	28	8.3

and Private school students in Relation to their Economic Status at secondary level is rejected.

Figure-4

The Mean score of Mathematical Phobia test is highest in lowest economic status group (Table 6, Figure 4) and decreases with increase in economic status.

Major Findings

- There exists a significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia of Government and Private school students in relation to the management at the secondary level. The Mean score shows that the Government school

students have higher Mathematical Phobia than their private counterparts at secondary level.

- There exists a significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in relation to Age group at secondary level. The Mean score of Mathematical Phobia test is highest in the age group of age more than 14 years (12.8). It shows that the students of age more than 14 have highest Mathematical Phobia as compared to students of age group below 14 years at secondary level. Also it cannot be said that the Mathematical Phobia increased with the age, since the students of age group up to 13 year students have high Mean score (11.94) than the students of age group of 14 years.
- There is a significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in relation to Sex at secondary level. The Mean score of Mathematical Phobia test of the boys is greater than girls. So the boys have more Mathematical Phobia than girls. It may be

because the girls are harder working than the boys.

- There is a significant difference between the Mean scores of Mathematical Phobia among Government and Private school students in relation to their socioeconomic status at secondary level. The mean score of Mathematical Phobia test is highest in the lowest economic status group and decreases with the increase in economic status. It may be justified as the students with high economic status have more facilities compared to the low economic status group. The students from higher economic group study in good schools; still if they have problems their parents can arrange tuition classes for them. Also the students from higher economic families have educated parents. They can solve their problems and give more attention than the other families.

Conclusion

This study reveals that the government schools secondary students have more Mathematical Phobia than their private counterparts. Boys have more Mathematical Phobia than girls. Students from lower economics status group have

more Mathematical Phobia than the students from higher economic status group.

It may be concluded that along with hard work there should be facilities to study Mathematics in terms of good teachers, and supportive family environment; if still there is some problem the student may be provided with tuition to overcome his/her problems.

There should be stress on the fundamentals of Mathematics right from primary classes so that students may be able to understand Mathematics properly and not create any kind of anxiety.

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